

lucose monitoring through nanoparticles: differences between optical and electrochemical analysis

Monitorización de glucosa mediante nanopartículas: diferencias entre análisis óptico y electroquímico

Cristóbal Espinoza, MD MgSc¹, <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8608-8338>

María Magdalena Tapia, MD, MgSc¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4011-2966>

Cristian Bustos, MD¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1297-4035>

María Angélica Coronel, MD¹ <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2858-4055>

Gladys Piña, MD² <https://orcid.org/0009-0009-3356-5298>

Ibeth Oñate, MD² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3870-2695>

Betzi Llanganate, MD² <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9103-8216>

Jorge Portacio, MD² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3803-9280>

Andrea Campaña, MD² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9111-1528>

Maribel Burgos, MD² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5865-503X>

Jairo Callay MD, MgSc² <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5172-5226>

¹Universidad Católica de Cuenca, Sede Azogues, Unidad Académica de Salud y Bienestar, Azogues, Ecuador.

²Centro Latinoamericano de Estudios Epidemiológicos y Salud Social, Cuenca, Ecuador.

Autor de correspondencia: Cristóbal Espinoza, MD, MgSc. Universidad Católica de Cuenca, Sede Azogues, Unidad Académica de Salud y Bienestar, Azogues, Ecuador. Correo electrónico: cristobal.espinoza@ucacue.edu.ec

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Abstract

Constant glycemic monitoring is fundamental for adequate management of diabetes mellitus. Current methods for this surveillance have several limitations, especially the painful sampling and the inability to perform measurements when the patient sleeps. As a result, adherence to the monitoring is often low, impairing the assessment of treatment efficacy. In order to overcome this problem, newer products focus on continuous glucose measurement through the implementation of nanosensors and nanomaterials. Electrochemical and optical glucose sensors have evolved significantly with nanotechnology, addressing the inherent problems of older generation sensors. Despite the overall good performance of both systems, clinical application remains far from consolidated. Poisoning effects from oxidation intermediates, instability at physiological pH, low specificity for glucose, and high costs are only some of the problems researchers currently face regarding the development of implantable continuous glucose sensors. More research is needed, both for electrochemical and optical sensors, to gain enough clinical significance and applicability to fulfill patients' need for friendlier means of glucose monitoring. This review aims to define the molecular mechanisms of electrochemical and optical glucose nanosensors, and analyze the drawbacks, limitations, and challenges of each.

Keywords: Nanotechnology, nanosensors, nanomaterials, glucose monitoring, diabetes.

Resumen

El control glucémico constante es fundamental para el manejo adecuado de la diabetes mellitus de interés en pacientes con insulino-terapia. Los métodos actuales para esta vigilancia tienen varias limitaciones, especialmente el doloroso muestreo y la imposibilidad de realizar mediciones cuando el paciente duerme. Como resultado, la adherencia al seguimiento suele ser baja, lo que perjudica la evaluación de la eficacia del tratamiento. Para superar este problema, los productos más nuevos se centran en la medición continua de glucosa mediante la implementación de nanosensores y nanomateriales. Los sensores

de glucosa electroquímicos y ópticos han evolucionado significativamente con la nanotecnología, abordando los problemas inherentes de los sensores de generaciones anteriores. A pesar del buen desempeño general de ambos sistemas, la aplicación clínica está lejos de consolidarse. Los efectos adversos de los intermedios de oxidación, la inestabilidad en el pH fisiológico, la baja especificidad para la glucosa y los altos costos son solo algunos de los problemas que enfrentan los investigadores actualmente con respecto al desarrollo de sensores de glucosa continuos implantables. Se necesita más investigación, tanto para sensores electroquímicos como ópticos, para obtener suficiente relevancia clínica y aplicabilidad para satisfacer la necesidad de los pacientes de medios más amigables para monitorear la glucosa. Esta revisión tiene como objetivo definir los mecanismos moleculares de los nanosensores de glucosa electroquímicos y ópticos, y analizar los inconvenientes, limitaciones y desafíos de cada uno.

Palabras clave: Nanotecnología, nanosensores, nanomateriales, monitorización de glucosa, diabetes mellitus.

Diabetes mellitus (DM) remains the leading cause of mortality and reduced life expectancy worldwide. Evidence shows that the overall burden of DM has steadily increased since 1990. The International Diabetes Federation (IDF) estimated that over 450 million adults lived with DM worldwide in 2017, a figure set to increase to over 700 million by 2045 if effective prevention measures are not taken¹. Moreover, diabetic patients have a 2 to 3-fold increased all-cause mortality². The presence of DM is strongly correlated with increased mortality from infections, CVD, stroke, cancer, and many others³. However, proper glycemic management has shown an important decrement in the overall morbimortality associated with DM⁴. Therefore, it is imperative to take early preventive measures to lengthen patients' life expectancy and significantly increase their quality of life. Constant glycemic control is fundamental for these goals⁵.

At present, glucose monitoring requires patients to obtain a blood sample, typically via a finger prick; blood is then placed onto a sensor test strip, ultimately giving blood glucose concentration through an electronic device⁶. Most of these sensors are based on electrochemical enzymatic measurements, providing rapid and accurate measurements without needing laboratory intervention⁷. However, these methods have several limitations, especially the painful sampling and the inability to perform measurements when the patient sleeps⁸. In order to overcome this problem, newer products focus

on continuous glucose measurement through the implementation of nanosensors and nanomaterials⁹.

Glucose sensors are divided into two big families, electrochemical sensors and optical sensors. Electrochemical glucose sensors rely on the electro-oxidation of glucose, which is then transduced into a quantifiable electrical signal. Despite being the oldest method, it remains equally effective¹⁰. However, optical sensors offer a direct, real-time measure of glucose, which better pairs with the goal of continuously monitoring glucose. Non-enzymatic glucose sensors based on fluorescence and surface plasmons resonance (SPR) currently boast the most evidence¹¹. This review aims to define the molecular mechanisms of electrochemical and optical glucose nanosensors, and analyze the drawbacks, limitations, and challenges of each.

Electrochemical and optical sensors: molecular basis and evolution

Electrochemical glucose sensors were first introduced in 1962 by Leland C. Clark. They were based on three essential components: a biological recognition element, the electrochemical transducer, and the signal processing system. This particular model had a glucose oxidase (GOx) with a modified platinum (Pt) electrode¹². The argument behind electrochemical glucose sensors is to convert glucose oxidation into a quantifiable electrical signal in the form of current or voltage to process and display it as a measurable unit in the electronic device. Another enzymatic system used in these devices was the glucose-1-dehydrogenase (GDH) and the oxidized form of pyrroloquinolinequinone (PPQ); however, the latter lacked specificity for glucose oxidation when compared to GOx. As a result, the GOx system has been historically preferred for this purpose¹³.

Essentially, GOx catalyzes glucose oxidation by molecular O₂ with the subsequent production of gluconic acid and hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). Then, the Pt electrode comes into play by oxidizing the H₂O₂, producing an electron flow proportional to the amount of glucose in the sample¹⁴. Nonetheless, this first-generation system greatly depends on O₂ concentration. Thus, variations of O₂ in biological fluids can significantly modify the performance of first-generation devices¹⁴. This issue was addressed by replacing the O₂ with a non-physiological redox mediator able to transport electrons from the GOx to the sensing electrode, eliminating the O₂ prerequisite¹⁵.

Afterwards, the need for a mediator was eliminated with the development of a direct electron transport system, the point at which gold nanoparticles and other nanomaterials were implemented to effectively stabilize GOx¹⁶. While this adjustment successfully overcame the oxygen issue, GOx instability was still a problem; moreover, given the complex processes needed to immobilize the GOx, chemical deformation became a problem during the manufacturing, storage, and use of these devices¹⁷.

Recently, non-biological catalysts have gained significant attention for glucose detection because, theoretically, these models can overcome all the limitations of the 1st to 3rd generation glucose sensors. These non-enzymatic glucose sensor models are based on nano-structured metals, metal-oxides, metal-organic frameworks (MOF), and metal azolate frameworks (MAF)¹⁸.

Later still, efforts were made to move towards non-biological models, as biological components require significant effort for stabilization¹⁰. As a result, many researchers have focused on developing glucose detection assays that do not rely on enzymes for substrate recognition. Direct detection of glucose oxidation at the electrode has been extensively studied; however, slow reaction kinetics and the need for enormous applied potentials significantly decrease specificity¹⁹. In that matter, nanomaterials have been implemented to develop direct oxidation glucose sensors. Copper, copper oxide²⁰, silver²¹, gold²², nickel²³, and palladium²⁴ are just some of the nanomaterials that have been studied in this field. Finally, carbon nanomaterials were introduced in the form of carbon nanofibers or nanotubes, significantly increasing the sensitivity and decreasing the working potential of the modified electrodes²⁵.

Regarding the performance of direct glucose oxidation sensors, Meng et al.²⁶ showed that palladium nanoparticles system could work at pH 7.4 and in clinical samples diluted with a buffer. However, this kind of models will probably not see any utility in clinical settings without significant work to improve the functionality of these models in undiluted samples, like those routinely obtained by patients¹⁰. Moreover, at physiological pH, most of these sensors suffer from a poisoning effect due to interference from intermediates of the oxidation process. Additionally, most direct glucose sensors have low selectivity for glucose, thus, oxidizing other organic molecules resulting in unstable current responses and, decreasing the accuracy of glucose concentration measurements in real samples²⁷. In conclusion, more research is needed to develop new nanomaterials that can non-enzymatically catalyze glucose oxidation free from poisoning effects and at a low cost.

On the other hand, optical sensors offer a more direct and real-time mechanism for glucose sensing. These methods rely on the change of intensity of the light upon binding of glucose molecules¹¹. In that matter, fluorescence spectroscopy-based glucose sensors do not measure glucose concentration directly; rather, it measures the signal from a molecular recognition fluorophore after glucose binding occurs. The variations of fluorescence intensity of these fluorophores are directly proportional to glucose concentration²⁸. Separately, SPR-based systems rely on glucose binding onto a plasmonic nanoparticle recognition compound which induces a variation in the angle of light reflectance. The variation of the angle of light reflectance is proportional to the concentration of glucose²⁹.

Fluorescence-based sensors (FBS) offer several advantages for continuous glucose monitoring. Firstly, FBS can optically interact with the sensors through the skin rather than depending on an implanted electrode system, minimizing the chances for infection or encapsulation of the device, which decreases the sensitivity for glucose, thus, compromising measurements accuracy³⁰. The FBS approach often involves a "smart tattoo" because sensors need to be implanted into the patient's skin. These implants are temporary and need replacement after a certain period. These sensors change their fluorescence properties in response to glucose; this signal is then translated by an optical sensor on the skin into a quantifiable unit, hence, eliminating the need for patients to take blood samples while allowing for continuous monitoring³¹.

Several FBS are based on polymeric nanosensors with incorporated boronic acid derivatives for glucose recognition. For example, a nanosphere based on N-isopropylacrylamide with phenylboronic acid derivatives and two fluorophores was synthesized by Zenkl et al.³². In the absence of glucose, the nanospheres hold the fluorophores close together, allowing efficient resonance energy transfer (RET). Upon glucose binding to the boronic acid derivative, the polymer swells, distancing the fluorophores from each other. The latter decreases RET, augmenting donor fluorescence and reducing acceptor fluorescence, which is measured by the optic sensor. This model has been improved by using multiple boronic acid derivatives and increasing fluorophore concentration, resulting in faster response time and better signal interpretation within the physiological glucose range³³.

Likewise, Shen et al.³⁴ prepared fluorescent carbon dots functionalized with boronic acid derivatives by hydrothermal carbonization of phenylboronic acid. This model used UV light as the excitation source for non-enzymatic glucose detection. Glucose binds boronic acid groups, inducing fluorescence quenching of carbon dots emission, directly proportional to glucose concentrations. Further, to widen the linear range to a clinically relevant glucose range, other authors incorporated copolymer microgels into the carbon dots. The resulting hybrid microgels could modify their dimensions according to glucose concentration variations, inducing quenching of the fluorescence intensity accordingly. As a result, these models provide a direct and continuous measurement of glucose concentration within and over the clinically relevant range at physiological pH³⁵.

Furthermore, Mai et al.³⁶ recently developed a Zinc oxide (ZnO) nanotube (NT) modified circuit board substrate for optical glucose monitoring. The sensor could measure glucose concentration by relying on the photoluminescence quenching of ZnO NTs. The mechanism involves using UV light to photoexcite the electrons in the ZnO NTs to facilitate the emission of photon energies. In the presence of glucose, both ZnO NTs and UV

light act as catalysts for glucose oxidation, decreasing fluorescence intensity, which is proportional to glucose concentration. Despite the overall good performance of FBS, their practical application as implantable devices is, at best, questionable. Firstly, their dependency on UV light for photoexcitation is hazardous; moreover, most of these systems display low stability and lifetimes. Additionally, the variation in the illumination/excitation wavelengths results in inaccurate glucose measurements. Further investigation is needed to solve these issues³⁷.

SPR-based systems provide an alternative to overcome the elemental problems of the FBS-based systems, since they use visible light as a means for photoexcitation instead of UV light. Essentially, SPR systems are based on the principle of oscillation of electrons at the dielectric interface, which can detect glucose via the variation of the local refractive index before and after glucose binding. Yuan et al.³⁸ developed a SPR glucose sensor using a mixed-self-assembled monolayer modified with gold-coated optical fibers. After optimizing its selectivity for glucose by creating a sandwich structure, the sensor effectively measured glucose concentration within a clinically relevant range. However, the binding of glucose to gold nanostructures can lead to their aggregation, which can decrease the accuracy of glucose detection. Moreover, this method is expensive and suffers from the same poisoning effect from oxidation intermediates at physiological pH³⁹.

D iabetes mellitus (DM) remains the leading cause of mortality and reduced life expectancy worldwide⁴⁰⁻⁴⁶. Traditional glucose monitoring is often painful and impractical for most patients, leading to low adherence or complete abandonment of the monitoring. This impairs the assessment of treatment efficacy. To overcome these obstacles, several attempts have been made to develop implantable devices that can continuously measure glucose without taking blood samples. Electrochemical and optical glucose sensors have evolved significantly with nanotechnology, addressing the inherent problems of the older generations' sensors. Despite the overall good performance of both systems, clinical application is still far from consolidated. Poisoning effects from oxidation intermediates, instability at physiological pH, low specificity for glucose, and high costs are only some of the problems researchers currently face regarding the development of implantable continuous glucose sensors. More research is needed, both for electrochemical and optical sensors, to gain enough clinical significance and applicability to fulfill patients' need for friendlier means of glucose monitoring.

References

1. Lin X, Xu Y, Pan X, Xu J, Ding Y, Sun X, et al. Global, regional, and national burden and trend of diabetes in 195 countries and territories: an analysis from 1990 to 2025. *Sci Rep*. 2020 Sep 8;10(1):14790.
2. Yang JJ, Yu D, Wen W, Saito E, Rahman S, Shu XO, et al. Association of Diabetes With All-Cause and Cause-Specific Mortality in Asia: A Pooled Analysis of More Than 1 Million Participants. *JAMA Netw Open*. 2019 Apr 19;2(4):e192696.
3. Bragg F, Holmes MV, Iona A, Guo Y, Du H, Chen Y, et al. Association Between Diabetes and Cause-Specific Mortality in Rural and Urban Areas of China. *JAMA*. 2017 Jan 17;317(3):280–9.
4. Landman GW, van Hateren KJ, Kleefstra N, Groenier KH, Gans RO, Bilo HJ. The relationship between glycaemic control and mortality in patients with type 2 diabetes in general practice (ZODIAC-11). *Br J Gen Pract*. 2010 Mar 1;60(572):172–5.
5. Mauras N, Fox L, Englert K, Beck RW. Continuous glucose monitoring in type 1 diabetes. *Endocrine*. 2013 Feb;43(1):41–50.
6. Oliver NS, Toumazou C, Cass AEG, Johnston DG. Glucose sensors: a review of current and emerging technology. *Diabet Med J Br Diabet Assoc*. 2009 Mar;26(3):197–210.
7. Wang J. Electrochemical glucose biosensors. *Chem Rev*. 2008 Feb;108(2):814–25.
8. Pickup JC, Zhi ZL, Khan F, Saxl T, Birch DJS. Nanomedicine and its potential in diabetes research and practice. *Diabetes Metab Res Rev*. 2008 Dec;24(8):604–10.
9. Wang TT, Huang XF, Huang H, Luo P, Qing LS. Nanomaterial-based optical- and electrochemical-biosensors for urine glucose detection: A comprehensive review. *Adv Sens Energy Mater*. 2022 Sep 1;1(3):100016.
10. Cash KJ, Clark HA. Nanosensors and nanomaterials for monitoring glucose in diabetes. *Trends Mol Med*. 2010 Sep 23;16(12):584–93.
11. Damborský P, Švitel J, Katrlík J. Optical biosensors. Estrela P, editor. *Essays Biochem*. 2016 Jun 30;60(1):91–100.
12. Heineman W, Jensen W, Leland C, Clark Jr. (1918–2005). *Biosens Bioelectron*. 2006 Feb 15;21:1403–4.
13. Ferri S, Kojima K, Sode K. Review of Glucose Oxidases and Glucose Dehydrogenases: A Bird's Eye View of Glucose Sensing Enzymes. *J Diabetes Sci Technol*. 2011 Sep 1;5(5):1068–76.
14. Yoo EH, Lee SY. Glucose Biosensors: An Overview of Use in Clinical Practice. *Sensors*. 2010 May 4;10(5):4558–76.
15. Putzbach W, Ronkainen N. ChemInform Abstract: Immobilization Techniques in the Fabrication of Nanomaterial-based Electrochemical Biosensors: A Review. *Sensors*. 2013 Apr 1;13:4811–40.
16. Bollella P, Gorton L, Ludwig R, Antiochia R. A Third Generation Glucose Biosensor Based on Cellobiose Dehydrogenase Immobilized on a Glassy Carbon Electrode Decorated with Electrodeposited Gold Nanoparticles: Characterization and Application in Human Saliva. *Sensors*. 2017 Aug;17(8):1912.
17. Ren S, Li C, Jiao X, Jia S, Jiang Y, Bilal M, et al. Recent progress in multienzymes co-immobilization and multienzyme system applications. *Chem Eng J*. 2019 Oct 1;373:1254–78.
18. Adeel M, Rahman MdM, Caligiuri I, Canzonieri V, Rizzolio F, Daniele S. Recent advances of electrochemical and optical enzyme-free

- glucose sensors operating at physiological conditions. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2020 Oct;165:112331.
19. Shamsipur M, Najafi M, Hosseini MRM. Highly improved electrooxidation of glucose at a nickel(II) oxide/multi-walled carbon nanotube modified glassy carbon electrode. *Bioelectrochemistry.* 2010 Feb 1;77(2):120–4.
 20. Wang G, Wei Y, Zhang W, Zhang X, Fang B, Wang L. Enzyme-free amperometric sensing of glucose using Cu-CuO nanowire composites. *Microchim Acta Int J Micro Trace Anal [Internet].* 2010 [cited 2022 Jul 12];(1–2). Available from: <https://www.scholarmate.com/A/nylfAb>
 21. Quan H, Park SU. Electrochemical oxidation of glucose on silver nanoparticle-modified composite electrodes. *Electrochimica Acta - ELECTROCHIM ACTA.* 2010 Feb 1;55:2232–7.
 22. Feng D, Wang F, Chen Z. Electrochemical Glucose Sensor Based On One-Step Construction of Gold Nanoparticle–Chitosan Composite film. *Sens Actuators B Chem.* 2009 May 1;138:539–44.
 23. Wang X, Zhang Y, Banks CE, Chen Q, Ji X. Non-enzymatic amperometric glucose biosensor based on nickel hexacyanoferrate nanoparticle film modified electrodes. *Colloids Surf B Biointerfaces.* 2010 Jul 1;78(2):363–6.
 24. Miao F, Tao B, Sun L, Liu T, You J, Wang L, et al. Amperometric glucose sensor based on 3D ordered nickel-palladium nanomaterial supported by silicon MCP array. *Sens Actuators B Chem.* 2009 Aug 18;141(1):338–42.
 25. Rathod D, Dickinson C, Egan D, Dempsey E. Platinum nanoparticle decoration of carbon materials with applications in non-enzymatic glucose sensing. *Sens Actuators B Chem.* 2010 Jan 7;143(2):547–54.
 26. Meng L, Jin J, Yang G, Lu T, Zhang H, Cai C. Nonenzymatic electrochemical detection of glucose based on palladium-single-walled carbon nanotube hybrid nanostructures. *Anal Chem.* 2009 Sep 1;81(17):7271–80.
 27. Bruen D, Delaney C, Florea L, Diamond D. Glucose Sensing for Diabetes Monitoring: Recent Developments. *Sensors.* 2017 Aug;17(8):1866.
 28. Klonoff DC. Overview of Fluorescence Glucose Sensing: A Technology with a Bright Future. *J Diabetes Sci Technol.* 2012 Nov 1;6(6):1242–50.
 29. Nguyen HH, Park J, Kang S, Kim M. Surface Plasmon Resonance: A Versatile Technique for Biosensor Applications. *Sensors.* 2015 May;15(5):10481–510.
 30. Wang Y, Vaddiraju S, Gu B, Papadimitrakopoulos F, Burgess DJ. Foreign Body Reaction to Implantable Biosensors. *J Diabetes Sci Technol.* 2015 Aug 25;9(5):966–77.
 31. Mou X, Lennartz MR, Loegering DJ, Stenken JA. Long-term calibration considerations during subcutaneous microdialysis sampling in mobile rats. *Biomaterials.* 2010 Jun;31(16):4530–9.
 32. Zenkl G, Mayr T, Klimant I. Sugar-Responsive Fluorescent Nanospheres. *Macromol Biosci.* 2008;8(2):146–52.
 33. Zenkl G, Klimant I. Fluorescent acrylamide nanoparticles for boronic acid based sugar sensing - from probes to sensors. *Microchim Acta.* 2009;166(1–2):123–31.
 34. Shen P, Xia Y. Synthesis-Modification Integration: One-Step Fabrication of Boronic Acid Functionalized Carbon Dots for Fluorescent Blood Sugar Sensing. *Anal Chem.* 2014 Jun 3;86(11):5323–9.
 35. Wang H, Yi J, Velado D, Yu Y, Zhou S. Immobilization of Carbon Dots in Molecularly Imprinted Microgels for Optical Sensing of Glucose at Physiological pH. *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces.* 2015 Jul 29;7(29):15735–45.
 36. Mai HH, Tran DH, Janssens E. Non-enzymatic fluorescent glucose sensor using vertically aligned ZnO nanotubes grown by a one-step, seedless hydrothermal method. *Microchim Acta.* 2019 Mar 16;186(4):245.
 37. Mello GPC, Simões EFC, Crista DMA, Leitão JMM, Pinto da Silva L, Esteves da Silva JCG. Glucose Sensing by Fluorescent Nanomaterials. *Crit Rev Anal Chem.* 2019 Nov 2;49(6):542–52.
 38. Yuan H, Ji W, Chu S, Qian S, Wang F, Masson JF, et al. Fiber-optic surface plasmon resonance glucose sensor enhanced with phenylboronic acid modified Au nanoparticles. *Biosens Bioelectron.* 2018 Oct 15;117:637–43.
 39. Aslan K, Lakowicz JR, Geddes CD. Nanogold-plasmon-resonance-based glucose sensing. *Anal Biochem.* 2004 Jul 1;330(1):145–55.
 40. Carpio Duran AL, Duran Medina MF, Andrade Valdivieso MR, Espinoza Dunn MA, Rodas Torres WP, Abad Barrera LN, et al. Terapia incretinomimética: evidencia clínica de la eficacia de los agonistas del GLP-1R y sus efectos cardio-protectores. *Latinoam Hipertens.* 2018;13(4):400–15.
 41. Espinoza Diaz C, Basantes Herrera S, Toala Guerrero J, Barrera Quilligana P, Chiluisa Vaca P, Sánchez Centeno P, et al. Explorando nuevas opciones farmacológicas en el tratamiento de la diabetes mellitus. *AVFT – Arch Venez Farmacol Ter.* 2019;38(6):754–7.
 42. Dávila LA, Escobar Contreras MC, Durán Agüero S, Céspedes Nava V, Guerrero-Wyss M, De Assis Costa J, et al. Glycemic Index Trends and Clinical Implications: Where Are We Going? *Latinoam Hipertens.* 2018;13(6):621–9.
 43. Maestre C, Tiso D´Orazio G, Contreras F. Relación entre hemoglobina glicosilada y descompensación en pacientes diabéticos tipo 2. *Diabetes Int.* 2011;3(1):17–25.
 44. Ortíz R, Garcés Ortega JP, Narváez Pilco VF, Rodríguez Torres DA, Maldonado Piña JE, Olivar LC, et al. Efectos pleiotrópicos de los inhibidores del SGLT-2 en la salud cardiometabólica de los pacientes con diabetes mellitus tipo 2. *Síndr Cardiometabólico.* 2018;8(1):27–42.
 45. Velásquez Z. E, Valencia B, Contreras F. Educación Diabetológica. *Diabetes Int.* 2011;3(1):4–7.
 46. Pérez Miranda PJ, Torres Palacios LP, Chasiliquin Cueva JL, Hernández Avilés GA, Bustillos Maldonado EI, Espinosa Moya JI, et al. Rol de la metformina en el tratamiento de la diabetes mellitus gestacional: situación actual. *AVFT – Arch Venez Farmacol Ter.* 2019;38(2):234–9.